

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

OPTIMIZING THE PERFORMANCE OF WEB APPLICATIONS ON THE CLIENT SIDE

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Abstract

This article focuses on optimizing the performance of web applications on the client-side with an emphasis on enhancing user experience (UX). It examines the concepts of web application performance, UX and their relationship. The main performance indicators are considered. It pays special attention to factors influencing client-side performance. It analyzes optimization techniques such as minification and resource concatenation, caching, lazy loading, image optimization, and the use of content delivery network.

Keywords: performance, web applications, user experience (UX), minification, caching, lazy loading, image optimization, frontend.

Introduction.

In the digital world, web applications play a crucial role in users' daily lives. From online stores to social networks, from banking services to educational platforms – all these applications strive to provide users with user-friendly interfaces and effective interaction experiences. Despite significant progress in technologies and design, many web applications face performance issues that can seriously impact user satisfaction and loyalty.

Frontend performance of web applications is a complex process that encompasses various factors, from page loading times to interface responsiveness. According to studies, users expect web pages to load in less than 3 seconds, and if the loading time exceeds this threshold, the likelihood of them leaving the site significantly increases [9]. This emphasizes the importance of optimizing frontend performance, as even small delays can result in significant losses in traffic and revenue, and can also impact user experience (UX). The purpose of this article is to review the main aspects of optimizing the performance of front-end web applications, with an emphasis on methods that can be implemented on the client side.

Main part. Performance and its impact on UX.

Web application performance is the ability of an application to quickly and efficiently process user re-

quests while maintaining smooth interaction. It includes the time taken to load pages, the speed of response to user actions, and overall interface responsiveness.

Web application performance is a crucial aspect determining the quality of UX. To evaluate performance, developers and analysts use several important metrics, each of which helps identify different aspects of the application. One of the most significant metrics is **page loading time**, which reflects how long it takes for a web page, including all its resources such as HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and images, to fully load. Another important metric is **response time**, which shows how long it takes from when a user initiates an action until the application begins to respond to that action [7]. Quick response creates a sense of responsiveness and comfort for users when interacting with the application.

Frame rate (FPS) also plays a significant role in perceived performance. This metric determines how many frames the application can display in one second. An optimal frame rate is around 60 FPS, ensuring smooth animations and transitions that are important for creating a positive UX.

Not less important is the time to first byte (TTFB), which measures the period from when a page is requested until the first byte of data is received from the server (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Checking the average TTFB value for a website

This indicator affects the overall loading time and can signal problems with the server or network delays [8]. **The total execution time of scripts** should also be considered when evaluating performance. This time, required for executing JavaScript code, affects the speed of user interaction with the frontend. Optimizing scripts can significantly speed up this process and improve the overall responsiveness of the application.

Understanding and monitoring performance indicators allows developers to manage web applications more effectively. Optimizing each of these aspects not only improves UX but also contributes to increased customer loyalty and business success overall.

Factors affecting client-side performance. Optimization techniques.

To successfully optimize the front-end performance of web applications, it is essential to start by measuring the current state and identifying major problem areas. Factors affecting client-side performance span a wide range of aspects, including resource optimization, network delays, script processing, and many others. Their understanding enables developers to create faster and more responsive applications, which in turn enhances user satisfaction and conversion rates.

One of the main factors is the **size and quantity of resources being loaded**. The larger and more complex they are, the more time it takes to load and process them. Large JavaScript files, for example, can slow down page loading because the browser must first download and then execute all scripts before the user can begin interacting with the application. Similarly, extensive CSS styles can not only slow down loading but also increase the time needed for page rendering [4].

The architecture of the application also has a significant impact on performance. Web applications can be implemented in various architectural styles, such as single-page applications (SPA) and multi-page applications (MPA). The download using the SPA takes place simultaneously and can dynamically update the content without completely reloading the page. This allows for more fluid and responsive interfaces, but can result in high initial loading times if not optimized. On the other hand, MPA load new pages with each request, which can be slower but allows only the resources needed for a specific page to be loaded. The choice between these architectural approaches depends on the specifics of the application and its performance requirements.

The use of third-party **libraries and frameworks** is also an important factor. While these tools can significantly speed up the development process, they can also add significant volume to the resources being loaded. Many libraries have large sizes, and if the application only uses a small part of their functionality, this can result in excessive loading, which negatively affects performance. Moreover, using multiple libraries can cause conflicts and increase JavaScript execution time, which also affects the responsiveness of the application. Therefore, it is important to carefully choose third-party solutions and monitor their relevance and effectiveness. Optimizing resource sizes, choosing the

right architecture, and carefully using third-party libraries can significantly increase loading speed and interface responsiveness, which in turn improves UX and contributes to business success.

Two interrelated techniques that allow reducing the amount of data loaded are **minification and resource concatenation**. Minification involves removing unnecessary symbols from CSS and JavaScript files, such as spaces, comments, and line breaks. This allows for a significant reduction in file sizes, making them faster to load. Resource concatenation complements minification by allowing developers to group multiple files into one. This reduces the number of HTTP requests needed to load a page and, accordingly, reduces the waiting time for users. When the browser can load one large file instead of multiple small ones, this not only speeds up the process but also reduces server load, which is particularly important during high traffic conditions.

Another technique that can significantly speed up web application loading is **caching**. It allows browsers to save copies of resources such as images and styles, preventing them from being reloaded the next time they are visited. Caching settings can be adapted depending on the type of resource: static resources can be cached for a long time, while dynamic elements that are frequently updated require a short storage period. Proper caching configuration helps reduce server load and ensures faster page loading for returning visitors.

Lazy loading is another effective technique that allows content to be loaded only when it becomes visible to the user. This is particularly important for pages with a large number of images or media content. For example, images below the viewing area can be loaded only as the page is scrolled down. This not only reduces initial loading time but also saves bandwidth, which is particularly important for mobile users. This technique can be implemented using simple HTML attributes or JavaScript libraries, making it accessible to most developers.

Image optimization also plays a crucial role in improving web application performance. Different image formats offer different levels of compression and quality. Formats like JPEG and WebP provide better compression, allowing file sizes to be reduced without significant loss of quality. Adaptive images, loaded depending on the size of the device's screen, help save bandwidth and speed up loading, as users only receive images that match their devices. This is particularly relevant in the era of diverse devices with various screens and resolutions.

Using a content delivery network (CDN) is another effective method for improving web application performance. CDN allow resources to be hosted on servers located closer to the user, reducing latency during loading. This not only speeds up the process but also increases reliability, as users can access resources from the nearest nodes. Moreover, many CDN offer built-in caching and image optimization features, which further contribute to overall performance improvement.

Optimizing web application performance is a multifaceted task that requires a careful approach. Existing

techniques have their own advantages and disadvantages. The choice of optimization strategy should be well-founded and depend on specific tasks, as it can significantly impact page loading speed, interface responsiveness, and overall application efficiency (table 1).

Table 1. Optimization techniques for client-side web application performance, advantages, and disadvantages [2, 3]

Technic	Advantages for UX	Limitations and disadvantages
Minification and pooling of resources	Speeds up page loading, reduces waiting time, and improves the responsiveness of the interface.	It can complicate code debugging if tools for working with minified files are not used.
Caching	Reduces the loading time for repeat visitors, improves the overall speed of the application.	Incorrect settings can lead to stale content being served, negatively impacting user experience and data accuracy.
Lazy loading	Reducing page loading time, improving the initial display of content	Some users may not see the content if they do not scroll the page, which may cause dissatisfaction.
Image Optimization	Reduces image loading time, improves the quality of visual content	It may require additional efforts to select the right formats and implement adaptive images.
Using a CDN	Speeds up loading, reduces delays, and increases resource availability.	Dependence on third-party services, possible privacy issues

Optimizing the performance of web applications on the client-side is a critical task that must be approached with consideration for a multitude of factors. Techniques such as minification and resource concatenation, caching, lazy loading, image optimization, and the use of CDN can significantly improve loading speed and responsiveness of applications. These measures not only enhance UX but also contribute to better search engine rankings for web applications. Investing in performance optimization is a strategic move that helps developers create more efficient and competitive web applications.

Improving UX through optimization.

Web application optimization plays a pivotal role in creating a positive UX. In a world where users expect instant response and high loading speeds, developers must consider numerous factors influencing user interaction with the application.

Interactivity and responsiveness are fundamental elements of a successful web application. Interactivity refers to users' ability to interact with interface elements and receive immediate feedback for their actions. This can include animations, color changes on hover, pop-ups, and other dynamic elements. Responsiveness, on the other hand, pertains to the speed at which the application reacts to user actions. The faster the interface responds to commands, the more satisfactory the UX will be. Studies show that delays of more than one second can cause frustration and lead to app abandonment.

Performance directly impacts user satisfaction. Web applications that load quickly and respond to actions without delays create a more positive impression. Users who encounter slow page loading or long response times are likely to feel frustrated and may leave the application, resulting not only in lost customers but also potentially negative reviews that could harm the company's reputation. Improving performance through optimization not only enhances UX but also boosts conversion rates and customer retention.

Successful case studies underscore the importance of these aspects. For instance, **Amazon** found that each

additional second of page load time reduced conversions. In response, they implemented numerous optimization techniques, including resource minification and CDN usage, significantly reducing load times and increasing sales [5].

Another example is **Netflix** focus on performance, ensuring fast startup and smooth content playback. They employ adaptive streams and caching to guarantee high-quality service even at low internet speeds [6]. This commitment to performance has significantly contributed to their financial success, as evidenced by their revenues increasing from \$14,08 million in 2022 to \$14,87 million in 2023 [1]. Such growth highlights how enhancing user experience through technology directly impacts the company's bottom line.

These examples demonstrate that proper optimization of client-side web application performance can lead to significant UX improvements and enhanced business performance metrics.

Conclusion.

Optimizing the performance of web applications on the client-side is an important factor directly contributing to improved UX. In a highly competitive environment with rising user expectations, providing instant responsiveness and intuitive interfaces is crucial. Applying various optimization techniques such as resource minification, caching, lazy loading, and image optimization can significantly reduce load times and enhance application interactivity.

Improving performance not only creates a positive company image but also directly impacts user satisfaction, their likelihood of returning, and product recommendations. Therefore, for developers and companies striving to create high-quality web applications, optimizing performance should be a top priority. Ultimately, the quality of UX will be the determining factor of success in the digital world.

References:

1. Annual report / Netflix // URL: https://s22.q4cdn.com/959853165/files/doc_financials/2023/ar/Netflix-10-K-01262024.pdf (date of application: 18.09.2024).
2. Bobunov A. Yu. Optimization of performance and reliability of financial applications through innovative testing methods // *Innovacionnaya nauka*. 2024. № 6-1. P. 74-79.
3. Bukhtueva I. Enhancing Customer Experience with AI-Powered Personalization Techniques // *Innovacionnaya nauka*. 2024. № 4-1. P. 114-119.
4. Gao X. H., Ho K. K., Abbas F. S. Development and deployment of deep learning interface web applications: A review // *Applied Research*. 2023. Vol. 53. No. 12. P. 15923-15945.
5. Lu M., Pan L., Lu S. Cloud storage cost optimization from a user-centric perspective: Latest advances, taxonomy, and survey // *ACM Computing Surveys*. 2023. Vol. 55. No. 13s. P. 1-37.
6. Monsao A. C. B., Correa S. L., Viana A. C., Cardoso K. V. Combining recommendations with resource-aware and caching in the MEC era for enhancing user interaction with streaming video // *IEEE Transactions on Services Computing*. 2022. Vol. 16. No. 3. P. 1698-1712.
7. Ogarkov A. Application of big data analytics to improve business customer service // *Innovacionnaya nauka*. 2024. №7-1. P. 61-65.
8. Ponomarev E. Analysis of the impact of using mobile applications for bill payments on the timeliness of payments and financial discipline of users // *Cold Science*. 2024. № 5/2024. P. 5-14.
9. Xiligianni C., Doukas F.-R., Drivas I. C., Kouis D. Speed matters: What to prioritize when optimizing for faster websites // *Analytics*. 2022. Vol. 1. No. 2. P. 175-192.